

CONCEPT OF CONTROL SYSTEM AND WAYS OF SYSTEM DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *Management is a multi-meaning concept. It is used where it is necessary to maintain the stability of an object or to influence the transition of a system from one state to another. Therefore, the concept of management is used to describe the influence of the manager.*

Keywords: *tutor, student, tutor duties, functions, competencies.*

The types of management system can be distinguished: For example: people who are continuous performers of production manage individual machines, mechanisms, systems, technological processes in production, more precisely, individual elements in production processes.

Management problems are also studied by several disciplines. In particular, philosophy, history, economics, jurisprudence and psychology are engaged in revealing its specific aspects. Psychology studies both the object and the subject of management. A team of scientists, an individual, their psychological states, some of their processes and tasks, which are studied in psychological research, are said to be management objects. When the subject of management is studied, it usually means a managing person or a group of people.

Psychology studies the psychological foundations of the manager's activity and on this basis solves a number of problems, such as what psychological states and processes should be cultivated in subordinates for effective organization of work and making clear and correct decisions.

Management psychology is a part of social psychology, it teaches how to solve the problems of the leader in the field of management, and how to manage the team and the individual in general. This problem is studied by employees of different disciplines and different fields depending on its subject. For example: philosophy, psychology, pedagogy, sociology, etc. Cybernetics studies the general theory of control. Cybernetics (from the Greek word "kybernetike" means the art of steering a ship).

Management is directly related to social psychology, and primarily means managing a person and managing his activities through a person. The basis of management is social, legal, psychological and theoretical knowledge. The theory of management and its system are inextricably linked with the science of cybernetics. The theory of management has its own genesis and is primarily based on social life experiences.

Management is an art and art is a skill. Therefore, a person always needs to be managed. In management, the leader always has an object and conducts his activities based on the law, orders and instructions. In most cases, activity consists of a collection of messages. Management theory is based on laws, orders and instructions, and psychological knowledge is the main tool and method of management. Therefore, there is no clear border between management psychology and social psychology. In management activities, the leader regulates his social behavior. The peculiarity of

management activities is that if management activities are not carried out correctly, it is known to everyone that any decisions and instructions will be broken on the way.

There is a concept of legal function in management, which is the main legal method for proper management of subordinates and teams. And psychological knowledge is an auxiliary method in management.

Effective use of time in the management process is one of today's requirements. Time is an unstoppable process. A person who uses time effectively will be fruitful and blessed in his work. The concept of time management is not only a person's self-management, but also management of a team, a family. Effective use of time means avoiding meetings, red tape and useless work.

Behavior of the leader is one of the main categories in management theory and methodology. The most important component of the transaction is communication. In the management process, dealings are based on cooperative activities. Language and speech are the main weapons in this process. Effectiveness can be achieved only if the subordinate communicates with the leader in a legally correct and official manner. In the process of official communication, the leader is the leading subject, therefore, great demands are placed on the moral qualities of the leader and his dealings with subordinates. In management, the leader establishes relations with all classes of people. In the process of interaction, both subjects learn universal and national moral norms. The employee understands the etiquette mainly in the image of the leader. The behavior of the leader is also divided into formal and informal communication, as noted in the psychological and pedagogical literature.

The official communication of the leader is based on existing laws and directive documents. Informal communication is based on the laws of professional pedagogy and ethics, and this process is based on the leader's family upbringing. If the leader is able to create a healthy mental and spiritual environment in the team, the leader's demands and orders will not only be fulfilled, but will become the belief and habit of each team member, which will directly help the leader to fully develop a sense of control. If the leader allows illegality in his interaction and behavior with subordinates, objections and reprimands will arise among the employees, and a basis for discussion will be created between them. If the leader follows the rules of decency and decency during the interaction, he will make the interlocutor proud that he accepts orders and instructions. Some thoughtless thoughts, excessive actions, gestures of a leader in the process of management can damage his reputation. The behavior of the leader should be pedagogical, because under him there may be new employees, experienced employees, and older people.

The effectiveness of the leader's influence on the team members (in a positive sense) and control of the task assigned to the employee in managing the team is reflected in the demandingness of his principle. At the same time, a leader, regardless of his level, should be very demanding of himself and naturally gain respect by his personal example to others.

Management does not have to be a set of empty words and phrases, thinking about every word in management, and being able to listen to the words, thoughts, and opinions of other colleagues also serves to improve mutual relations in the team. As a result of excessive sending of instructions and orders by the leader, it causes them to remain on a simple paper and lose their power. The leader must always be a full supporter of the implementation of laws, and also be a kind of psychologist. Therefore, the leader is also a person who ensures the implementation of the law and carries out its control. If the employees were pure of heart, there would be no need for the leader to control the implementation of such a law and be strict when the time comes. But since

the employees were brought up in different families and environments, there is a sufficient level of indolence, laziness and indolence among them. "If you do good, they will be on your side, they will swear that everything is yours, but if there is danger, they will betray without hesitation".

The main task of the leader in management is to protect this community. The team will not forgive the leader who brought the team down and ruined it. When managing a team, a leader needs to be not only a theoretician, but also a practitioner. A leader can lead a team in two ways:

First, the leader is respected and loved by the team and they fulfill all the tasks given by him.

The second one obeys his orders because he is afraid of the leader, so the leader we fear and respect rules us as our beloved leader makes us obey him.

At the same time, leaders are guided by factors such as duty, intelligence, purpose, honor, morality, and affect their morale. For some leaders, duty or honor may prevail over all human factors. Therefore, the art of management is a very complex process. It is this leader who makes the nation live as a nation and the nation as a nation. But it is the team that makes the leader the leader. If there is mutual understanding and support between the team and the leader, the work of the team and the leader will be a blessing.

When we talk about the theory and methodology of management, management culture is one of the most important factors. Management culture includes legal and ethical standards, national traditions, and human spiritual wealth to one degree or another. . Management culture is measured by the leader's internal culture, outlook, psychology and level of pedagogical knowledge. Labor efficiency is important in management culture. It is a difficult process to clearly demonstrate efficiency, because the working hours of the manager are not regulated, that is, if work starts at 08:00 in the morning, this activity can continue until 22:00, 23:00.

It is known that, regardless of the goals and tasks, different systems of management show the unity of two systems: the managed and those who manage.

The object of management is a set of elements of production processes. This includes technical (technique and technology), economic (planning, finance, normal factors) and social (organization of workers and their relationship to the team) elements.

It should be noted that the first place in the set of elements is the accumulation of labor tools and resources used by people in the production process to create material well-being. People in the management system are not only one of its elements, but also the center where all the main links of the production management system converge.

In the field of management, human labor can be divided into two types: "Labor", which directly implements the production process, and "Activity", which is directed to the direct management of these processes. The first type of human labor activity appears as an object, and the second as a subject of management. From this, it can be concluded that management is primarily the management of people, and they, in turn, manage the means of production.

The relationship between management and management systems is considered as a relationship between people. But their management means not only management of employees, but also a direct purposeful influence on their relations in production.

The subject of management is links in production - a combination of various organizations, links, groups assigned management rules and obligations.

The entity in the management system is related to the development and implementation of decisions that ensure the achievement of the set goal. It is aimed at solving a set of special tasks

that includes the functions of production management on a scientific basis, researches are aimed at solving tasks related to design, planning, organizational, coordination, economic and management control problems.

The increase in the average annual salary occurs due to the fact that the worker fulfills the established norm of service, and the presence of unproductive costs in the salary. In addition, due to the change in the annual salary of one worker, the salary fund of workers was affected. It can be seen from the data that this year in the company, we can see that the financial situation of the workers has increased and that the material attention has increased, their material condition has improved. we can also observe.

In a broad sense, economic management means the management of economic objects, processes, and relationships. In this interpretation, the presence of the human factor in every part of management, the management factor involving people, seems invisible from the outside. It should be noted that the first place in the management system complex is the accumulation of labor tools and resources used by people in the production process to create material well-being. People in the management system are not only one of its elements, but also the center where all the main links of the production management system converge.

Employee management is a system of interconnected organizational, economic and social measures related to the normal development, implementation and effective use of workforce potential at the organizational level. Employee management is a continuous process. It is the reasons for employees to work and get a higher profit from it. So, it means that finally high results have been achieved in the activities of enterprises. Functionally, employee management is understood as all tasks and decisions related to work in the field of personnel, for example, selecting personnel, using them, improving their qualifications, paying for their work, firing, etc.

From an organizational point of view, this concept covers all persons and institutions responsible for working with personnel, for example, managers, personnel departments, production councils, trade unions.

In our view, human resource management means that people are the company's competitive advantage. It is necessary to deploy, develop and support them together with other resources. The purpose of this is to achieve the strategic goals of the enterprise.

Thus, the main element of the entire management system is the employee, who can be both an object and a subject of management at the same time. The reason why the employees of the organization act as an object is that they are the productive force, the main organizer of any production process. Therefore, the planning, formation, redistribution and rational use of human resources in production is the main content of employee management. The management of material elements of production is also considered from the same point of view.

A goal is a conscious idea of a result to be achieved through the directed efforts of a person in the process of interaction and communication.

Management system objectives are the starting point for planning. In essence, planning is the development of goals and objectives of organizations, which are clearly expressed in long-term and current plans.

The objectives are:

By scope of activity: global or general; local or private.

By relevance: relevant (priority) and irrelevant.

By level: senior and junior.

By time factor: strategic and tactical.

According to management functions: organization, planning, control and coordination goals.

By subsystems of the organization: economic, technical, technological, social, industrial, commercial, etc.

By topics: individual and group.

According to awareness: real and imaginary.

By accessibility: real and fantastic.

By hierarchy: top, middle, bottom.

Attitudes: interactive, indifferent (neutral) and competitive.

According to the object of interaction: external and internal.

Activity goals are of great importance in the management process.

1. The organization should make only decisions that fulfill the goals of its activity.

2. The global goal should be communicated to every leader and executive to prevent such activities that interfere with the achievement of the activity goals. This requires constant monitoring of the actual state of the system and its comparison with the goals and objectives of the organization.

Any organization should be designed in such a way that all activities in the system only fulfill the goals for which it was created.

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